

Political Science Analysis of Criminal Behavior and Theories Obtained from Sociological Research

Mustafa Kemal DEMİROGLU

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Abstract

It is very necessary to acquire a solid understanding of the three primary causes of criminal conduct in order to receive an education in the psychological foundations of criminal behavior. The first of these is called the psychodynamic hypothesis, and it is predicated on the idea that a person's experiences during their formative years have an effect on the likelihood that they will commit a crime in the future. The study of human behavior is the focus of the second technique, which is known as behavioral theory. Gabriel Tarde was the first person to carry out the research that was subsequently expanded upon by behavioral theorists through the use of behavior modeling and social learning. The cognitive theory is the third hypothesis, and its basic premise is that an individual's propensity to commit crimes is influenced by both the individual's view of the world and the manner in which that perception is shown (Jacoby, 2004). The second hypothesis is known as the behavioral theory, and its basic premise is that an individual's perception and the manner in which they exhibit it are intertwined (Jacoby, 2004). In a similar vein, why is there a need for unlawful activity in the culture that we live in? Because criminologists spend a lot of time focusing on problems that are associated with the legal system, they go to considerable lengths to discover

solutions to questions like these. In point of fact, providing a response that is rational and acceptable to the issue of what motivates people to commit crimes is not a simple undertaking to accomplish. Notwithstanding this, individuals have been searching for solutions to their problems for a very long time (Jacoby, 2004). It is essential to be aware that individuals engage in criminal behavior for a variety of reasons, not just one, and that these factors all play a role in the game. This is the case because there is no single explanation for why people engage in illegal behavior (Conklin, 2007). One of the most important explanations is founded on psychological theories, many of which concentrate on the connection between deviant behavior and aspects such as IQ, personality, learning, and education. This is one of the major explanations. These concepts constitute one of the most significant justifications, and you may find them here. It is essential to incorporate psychological points of view if one is having a conversation about factors that may play a role in the development of criminal behavior.

Keywords: *Human Psychology, Criminal Psychology, Criminal Behaviors, Crime Theories, Political Science and Criminal Sociology*

Introduction

It is very necessary to have a working understanding of the three primary causes of criminal conduct when one is seeking an education in the psychological underpinnings of criminal behavior. The first of these is called the psychodynamic hypothesis, and it is predicated on the idea that a person's experiences during their formative years have an effect on the likelihood that they would commit a crime in the future. The study of human behavior is the focus of the second technique, which is known as behavioral theory. Gabriel Tarde was the first person to carry out the research that was subsequently expanded upon by behavioral theorists through the use of behavior modeling and social learning. The cognitive theory is the third hypothesis, and its basic premise is that an individual's propensity to commit crimes is influenced by both the individual's view of the world and the manner in which that perception is shown (Jacoby, 2004). The second hypothesis is known as the behavioral theory, and its basic premise is that an individual's perception and the manner in which they exhibit it are intertwined (Jacoby, 2004). In a nutshell, behavioral theory investigates

how a person's perception of the outside world affects the decisions and behaviors that that individual chooses to engage in. This influence may have a favorable or unfavorable outcome. When it comes to the formulation of psychological hypotheses, personality and IQ are key factors that should be taken into consideration as crucial variables. When seen in their whole, these five theories or attributes (psychodynamic, cognitive, behavioral, personality, and IQ) provide intriguing insights into the reasons why a person may commit crime (Schmallegger, 2008).

Researchers who are seeking for a single answer should approach with care since there is no silver bullet that can cure the problem of crime. Nonetheless, one must resist the temptation to presume that there is just a single rationale for a person's criminal behavior.

[Initial Investigations Related to the Subject](#)

Charles Goring, a researcher who lived from 1870 until his death in 1919, was the one who first noticed a connection between criminal behavior and mental impairments. During the period that Goring worked in England, his medical experiments were performed on over 3,000 condemned criminals in that country. It should be underlined that Goring does not see any difference between individuals who have done crimes and those who have not committed crimes in his view. Despite this, he made the startling discovery that criminals were far more likely than non-criminals to demonstrate poor social conduct, mental instability, and ignorance in their actions. It is generally agreed that Gabriel Tarde (1843–1904) is the second pioneer of the discipline. During the years 1843 and 1904, he was alive. He was of the opinion that individuals gained information from one another and, over time, began to emulate one another as a result of this. It is interesting that Tarde mentioned that even if just one person out of a hundred feels they are creative or inventive, they are more inclined to emulate what they see other people doing (Jacoby, 2004).

[Psychodynamic Theory](#)

Those who subscribe to the psychodynamic school of thinking assert that an individual's personality is founded on unconscious mental processes that start during the formative years of the person's life and continue throughout their adulthood. They assert that this is the situation. Sigmund Freud (1856–1939), who is widely regarded as the pioneer in the area of psychoanalysis, is the one who came up with the idea for the very first time. This theory lays a significant amount of stress on human identity, ego, and superego since these are the three structures or components

that make up the human psyche. The superego is, by a significant margin, the most significant of the three. Freud (1933) held the belief that a person's identity is representative of a person's unconscious biological desires for food, sex, and other necessities that continue throughout life. Freud believed that a person's identity is representative of a person's desires for food, sex, and other necessities. One way to think about a person's identity is as the most fundamental component of their mental structure, which is already present in them from birth. This method of thinking about a person's identity is referred to as the core of their personality.

[Criminal Behavior Theories Based on Psychology](#)

The idea that the id is preoccupied with one's own immediate satisfaction or gratification in general, without concern for the wellbeing of others, is the most essential component of this philosophy. The term "pleasure principle" refers to this idea, which, when examining criminal behavior, is almost universally considered to be the single most essential notion. It is extremely frequent to come across accounts of criminals who just care about themselves and have no regard for the welfare of others, and this may happen whether you are looking at research or reading the news. This is a sad truth that must be faced. Is it feasible for both male and female offenders to take quick action in response to the urge to have their needs met? It is generally agreed upon that the ego is the second component of a person's personality and that it emerges throughout the formative years of a person's life. It is generally agreed that the ego is the second aspect that makes up a person's personality. It is generally known, for instance, that children will act out in the form of a tantrum when they discover that their demands cannot be satisfied in a timely manner.

Freud (1933) proposed that the ego serves as a kind of compensation for the demands of the id, directing a person's activities and behaviors so that they operate within the confines of society. In other words, the ego ensures that a person is able to function normally within the constraints of society. This was accomplished by ensuring that the person's actions and behaviors were directed in such a manner as to enable them to function within the limitations of society. This was done by ensuring that the individual had access to the necessary resources. When it comes to decision-making, the ego might consult the reality principle for assistance. The superego is the third component of a person's psyche and develops as a result of the individual's assimilation of the moral standards and values of the society in which he lives, his parents, and other significant people

in his life, such as friends and clergy. The superego is responsible for guiding the individual's behavior and making decisions. Ethical concerns are of primary importance to the superego. The individual's superego functions as a judge who passes judgment on the person's acts and behaviors. Its duty is to fulfill the role of a judge (Freud, 1933). The ego works as a mediator between the superego's emphasis on adhering to stringent moral standards and the craving for immediate fulfillment. It is reasonable to presume that people of all ages, including children and adults, have some understanding of morality and other notions that are connected to it. Yet, supporters of the psychodynamic theory would say that if a person commits a crime, it is because his or her superego is not formed, and hence the individual is culpable of committing the crime.

Psychodynamic Theory

In a nutshell, the psychodynamic hypothesis asserts that those who are more inclined to participate in criminal activity are those who are angry and disappointed. It would appear that individuals are quite frequently occupied with reflecting about incidents that took place in their lives when they were still very young. It is the most common factor that contributes to a neglected, unhappy, or miserable upbringing, which is what most often results in a criminal having a weak (or deficient) ego. A lack of love and/or attention is the most common factor that contributes to a neglected, unhappy, or miserable upbringing. The absence of affection and/or care is the defining characteristic of an upbringing that is either negligent, sad, or unpleasant. This is due to the fact that the offender did not receive sufficient amounts of affection and/or attention when he was younger. According to the conclusions of a body of research, having a fragile sense of self is connected to possessing negative or nonexistent social views, being immature, and being dependent on the acceptance of other people. This is the most significant conclusion that can be reached based on the findings of the investigation. Individuals who have a low opinion of their own worth, according to the findings of other studies, are more likely to engage in risky behaviors, such as substance abuse.

They are unable to behave in a manner that is acceptable within the context of society because they are unable to develop meaningful relationships with other people. In addition to this, children who have been abused are at an increased risk of developing mental diseases such as schizophrenia or depression in later life.

After everything is said and done, bullies put themselves in risk by participating in aggressive conduct from a young age, but without substantial penalties for doing so. This behavior puts them in the path of potential harm. Particularly throughout the adolescent years of a person's life, being involved in challenging relationships has the potential to have a substantial influence on the development of that person's personality. Both the errors we have made in our own lives and the sadness we have felt as a result of betrayal or separation can have a devastating effect on our perception of who we are and our level of self-confidence. Mistakes we have made in our own lives can have a devastating effect on our level of self-confidence. In addition, the first sexual encounter is significant for the reasons that have been discussed thus far, as well as for the ones that were discussed in the item that came before this one. The humiliation that some of us are presently subjected to has the potential to influence the way in which the mental and sexual aspects of our bodies will grow in the years to come. This is due to the fact that our bodies are comprised of a greater variety of components than our intellect.

- 1. In the case of men, failures in sexual life typically lead to a desire to replace reproductive power with psychic aggression.*
- 2. In the case of women, failures in sex life rarely lead to the same desire. In the case of women, disappointments in sex life almost never result in this kind of desire.*

This view is founded on the fact that he is unable to demonstrate either of these two facts. Last but not least, adults provide a threat to a kid who is still developing into an adult in the process of becoming an adult. Abuse of a teen's body or any aspect of their sexuality, in any manner, is extremely destructive to their identity and can occur at any moment over the course of their development. A circumstance in which an individual was formerly subjected to sexual abuse is an example of the phenomenon known as the "cycle of violence," which is referred to by the phrase. An adult who was the victim of physical and sexual abuse while they were children continues to replicate the same mindset as they had when they were younger. Victims are more likely to seek vengeance for the childhood trauma they suffered from innocent bystanders than from the individual who was directly responsible for the damage, which can lead to antisocial conduct. Feelings of insecurity and resentment can contribute to antisocial behavior. This is due to the fact

that victims are more prone to seek retribution for the traumatic experiences they went through as children.

When children reach the age when they begin to be significantly influenced by the thoughts and perspectives of their friends, it is possible that a terrible friendship will indeed result in abnormal behavior. This is the case for children who have reached the age when they can be significantly influenced by the thoughts and perspectives of their friends. As children reach this age, they are at a point in their development where they are beginning to be greatly impacted by the beliefs and attitudes of their peers. At this point in their development, youngsters start to think about things on their own. It is inevitable that individuals will choose the incorrect road, that acceptable norms will be lost or destroyed, and that, as a consequence, there will be contradictions in publicly recognized standards. This is due to the fact that people might be misled by improper role modeling. A strong desire to comply with society's expectations and conventions is one of the primary motivating factors that lead to delinquency among young people. Nonetheless, the vast majority of young people who are members of so-called "gangs" are not often involved in violent crimes such as rape or murder. Instead, they frequently participate in illegal activities such as stealing, assaulting others, or trafficking drugs.

In addition, when we participate in unlawful behavior as a member of a larger group, the weight of our individual guilt is immediately diminished. The phrase "bystander effect" not only refers to the inability to help when people are surrounded, but it also refers to how likely we are to behave inappropriately when a crime is committed in a group setting. This is because bystanders are more likely to behave in an inappropriate manner when there are other people around. This is since we believe we are unable to make a difference. The 150 people who followed him around are probably the most well-known example of mass influence. Because the members of the group are instructed by their leader to carry out murder in accordance with the group's ideals, the organization can be held accountable for these killings.

As was said previously, the way a kid is brought up by his or her parents has a tremendous influence on the manner in which that child matures into an individual. Children whose parents are addicted to drugs or alcohol have a significantly increased risk of developing problematic behaviors as adults. A significant component that contributes to the development of a person's sense of norms and morality is exposure to an environment in which incorrect behavior is

frequently seen as acceptable. This circumstance not only contributes to discord within the family but also makes the child's life more difficult because there are no positive role models for the youngster to admire and emulate. This is one of the reasons why the youngster isn't happy, and it's an element that contributes to the problem.

With all that has been discussed up to this point, it should come as no surprise that the environment plays a substantial role in shaping antisocial conduct. Humans are not born to commit crimes; rather, the passage of time and exposure to traumatic events make them into lifelong criminals. Consequently, it is vitally necessary to determine whether individuals should be penalized for their acts.

[Should we throw those in need behind bars, or are there other solutions we can follow instead of the issue?](#)

We are of the belief that the only method that has the capacity to successfully eliminate antisocial conduct is the employment of physical punishment, and as a result, this tactic is utilized in the great majority of countries. But, as we discovered during the course of the unit, the administration of punishment needs to take place in a timely fashion. However, there are several incompatibilities that prevent us from putting them into operation at this moment.

Due to the potentially lengthy nature of the appeal process, the consequences of the sentence will be less severe while it is pending. Despite this, the beneficence of today's society has contributed to the formation of a system that allows a sizeable number of offenders to survive. As a consequence of this, there is a chance that rehabilitation will result in a more favorable conclusion. While working with offenders, therapists frequently employ a diverse array of psychological strategies. These technologies, which are built on cognitive and behavioral approaches, place an emphasis on relearning and retraining as a means of discovering and altering the factors that underlie the antisocial conduct of offenders. Due to the fact that they are not employed for an extended period of time, it is impossible to determine whether or not they are more successful than more conventional forms of punishment. But there is no question that the probability of these technical advances becoming the new answer to the problem is a big one. This is something that cannot be disputed. It is not possible to rule out this possibility. On the other hand, it is a well-known fact that it is far simpler to steer clear of an issue totally than it is to make the effort to deal with the consequences of that problem. Because of the significant amount of psychological

development that is currently taking place, it will be possible for us to identify potentially delinquent children in the future at much earlier stages than was previously possible. This is a significant improvement over the situation that existed in the past. In today's society, particular sections of the police force have been established with the primary mission of locating and assisting youngsters whose behaviors are similar to those described earlier in the article. The protection of children was the primary motivation behind the creation of these agencies. Depression, failed attempts at suicide, and learning difficulties are all patterns that are likely indicative of a person's propensity to engage in criminal action. These patterns can indicate that a parent is abusing drugs or that there is violence in the home from a partner or another family member. Because most of this information is already documented in police databases, providing help to these young people from the very beginning is a rather straightforward process.

Also, the introduction of mandatory personality examinations into the curricula of educational institutions is likely to be of great benefit. Because some of their characteristics change, it is likely that the information gathered from them does not immediately lead to suspected criminals. "It is practically hard to identify them at a young age, although it is feasible. The process of locating them will become noticeably easier in the not-too-distant future. For instance, if there is information that has been documented concerning the suspects' mental health, this might be helpful. With all that has been discussed up to this point, it is abundantly evident that a genetic predisposition toward criminal conduct and hereditary characteristics that contribute to criminal behavior are the only factors that contribute to criminal activity.

Research and Methods

This idea is essential for not only comprehending the dynamics of aberrant behavior but also for figuring out the treatment plan that will be most successful in curing the illness. Due to the fact that psychology is being discussed, it is more important than ever before for academics who are currently working in this field to develop particular tools that can diagnose, treat, and prevent criminal conduct. It is of the utmost importance to study the possibility of not only preventing the loss of life among potential victims but also providing assistance to young offenders. Because achieving both of these objectives is of the utmost importance, it is critical to make every effort to protect the lives of people who could become victims in the future. Second, we need to keep in mind that even though we have a propensity to place responsibility on the wrongdoers for every

issue that emerges, any one of us might unknowingly play a role in the alteration of the personality of another individual. This is something that we must keep in mind.

This is something that we need to keep in mind, despite the fact that we have a propensity to place blame on others for any difficulties that develop. In the field of psychology, developmental psychology is a sub-specialty that studies the factors and processes that affect a person's development over the course of his life (Hurlock, 2001). This presents various distinct reasons for criminal conduct; the most significant of these theories is that delinquent behavior happens as a result of developmental issues such as a lack of social skills or attachment difficulties. In addition to this, this offers an explanation for illegal action in a number of distinct ways. The field of developmental psychology, which investigates the elements that play a role in the evolution of behavior, lays a great amount of attention on the question of whether or not a criminal is "made" or "born." This polarity holds a pivotal position at the center of the field.

Explaining Antisocial Behavior

When attempting to explain antisocial conduct, it is feasible to better understand the underlying elements that lead to antisocial behavior by applying the concepts of developmental psychology. This makes it possible to explain antisocial behavior. Because of this, it will be much simpler to put an end to such conduct and deal with it in the proper manner. We will utilize the idea of attachment in connection to a person's emotional, moral, and prosocial growth as a means of attempting to explain antisocial conduct. Specifically, we will be focusing on how attachment affects a person's sense of belonging. In addition, terminology that will depict the difficulties encountered by young offenders across the whole criminal justice system will be incorporated. This will be done in addition to the measure that is now being considered. When we speak about a person's connection to another, we are referring to the emotional link that exists between those two persons. When we talk of attachment, what we really mean is this link between people (Ainsworth, 1973). 1973 was the year when Ainsworth's results were first published. Because it takes into consideration both a person's history and the circumstances in which they presently find themselves, attachment theory provides a framework for the study of aggressive conduct. This is because it takes into account both the person and the situation. This is due to the fact that the theory takes into account a person's history in addition to the circumstances in which they find themselves at the present time (Ogilvie et al. 2014).

According to Bowlby's theory (1944), the lack of a maternal figure in a child's childhood might lead to delinquent and criminal behavior. This is due to the fact that parents frequently serve as the foundation for later interactions. This is due to the fact that parents frequently serve as the groundwork for later relationships. According to this hypothesis, which is sometimes referred to as the mother deprivation theory, the lack of a mother in the life of a kid may be the root cause of antisocial and delinquent actions in that child at a later age. Even if there is a parent figure in the kid's life, the youngster may still be deemed to be deprived if he does not receive sufficient attention and does not have a strong link with the parent figure that resides within him.

When children and teenagers do not have strong emotional relationships with caring and loving parents, this increases the risk that they may participate in unlawful activities (Bowlby, 1951). 1951 was the year when Bowlby released the results of his investigation. If a young man does not have someone in his life who can serve as a suitable substitute for his mother, it is possible that as he matures, he may acquire a profound antipathy against females. This is especially important to keep in mind if the child does not have a mother. Because of this, there is a chance that when the kid is an adult, he or she may participate in aggressive conduct with other women. Even if the child does not have another significant male figure in his life to take the place of the absent father, he may still try to blame the mother for the current circumstances. It has been proven that parents who do not provide proper care for their children throughout the formative years of the child are more likely to have adolescents who engage in aggressive behaviors (Herren kohl et al. 2000).

According to the findings of research that was conducted by Ainsworth in 1978, the key factor that determines the degree to which a young infant feels connected to the world is the manner in which the child's mother interacts with the child. It is not inconceivable that a mother who is not very sensitive may give birth to a child who is excessively devoted to others and apprehensive about the future. The absence of effective parental supervision is the only component that, when combined with the others, may more correctly predict future criminal conduct (Smith & Stern, 1997).

Many studies have indicated that children who display antisocial conduct are more likely to have parents who do not know or care about their children's location. These parents are also more likely to have antisocial behavior themselves. On the other hand, parents who are aware of their child's whereabouts always stand in contrast to this. Children who engage in antisocial behavior are

statistically less likely to be produced by parents who are always aware of their child's location and who monitor their activities. These parents stand in sharp contrast to others who are always aware of their children's locations, which is an important parenting skill. If you administer punishment in an erratic or inconsistent manner, you should also prepare yourself for the possibility of improper behavior. It's not out of the question. There is a correlation between the use of severe forms of parental discipline, such as physical punishment, and an increase in the risk that the kid would engage in antisocial conduct later in life (Haapasalo & Pokela, 1999). (Haapasalo and Pokela, 1999).

According to the findings of Newson's (1989) study, forty percent of the juvenile delinquents in their study had been subjected to physical punishment before the age of eleven, but only fourteen percent of those who had not been exposed to corporal punishment had not been subjected to it. McCord (1979) saw that parents who are apathetic about and do not embrace their children are more likely to have children who grow up to be delinquents. This is because these parents are less likely to model appropriate behavior for their children. This is because these parents are more likely to pass on their negative attitudes to their children. There is a chance that the love and support of a parent could protect a child from the sad things that happen when they are physically punished. According to the findings of the research that was conducted by McCord, the rate of boys who were found guilty was significantly higher in those whose mothers were uninterested, unsupported, and physically violent than in those whose mothers were affectionate. This was the case even when comparing the two groups of boys with the same characteristics. After examining the similarities and differences between the two boy bands, we came to this conclusion. This was the conclusion that could be drawn from the study when it was compared to the percentage of boys whose moms' showed affection. According to the findings of Smallbone and Dadds (1998), sexual offenders reported having less stable maternal relationships with their moms when they were young compared to those who did not commit crimes of a sexual nature. This was demonstrated to be the case even though both sets of children had strong ties with their moms. This stood in sharp contrast to the experiences of most of the people as a whole. The individuals who reported having difficulties with their moms were the ones whose children from their own families had been sexually abused, whereas those who reported having problems with their dads were the ones whose children from their own families had been sexually abused.

Argument

Prosocial development is a term that is used to describe actions that are intentionally aimed at assisting the growth of other individuals. This kind of behavior is tolerated for the good of society. If children are taught to copy the actions of adults, there is a greater likelihood that the children will behave in a socially responsible manner when they get older. One of the most significant components of empathizing is being able to recognize the mental state as well as the emotions experienced by another person. A psychopath is a sort of criminal that is claimed to be unable to empathize with people who have been wounded as a direct result of criminal activity. Psychopaths are a subtype of the criminal population. The notion of the "sanity mask", a classification of some psychopathic features, was initially suggested by Clerkley (1941). (1941). These characteristics include a flawed theory of mind, an inability to think in an ethical or compassionate manner, a lack of self-awareness, as well as knowledge of one's own deficiencies. A considerable proportion of offenders may be characterized by little or no sympathy or care for the victims of their acts. Because of this, the great majority of treatment programs for sexual offenders incorporate some kind of instruction on how to have empathy. Because having empathy is a talent that can be learned. The ability to comprehend another person's mental processes in order to account for and anticipate their conduct is one of the interpretations of the phrase "theory of mind."

Even at a very young age, children and teenagers begin to create their own viewpoints in their minds. Nevertheless, Keenan and Ward (2000) argue that sexual offenders have a conciliatory theory of mind, indicating that it may not have been completely established as a youngster. This suggests that those who commit these offenses are more likely to engage in sexually improper conduct. This indicates that those who participate in sexually improper behavior are at an increased risk of engaging in sexually risky behavior themselves. According to Kohlberg (1984), the evolution of morality may be broken down into three separate phases at significant junctures along the course of its development. In early childhood, children go through a stage of development known as pre-conventional morality. At this time period, individuals are able to understand, in addition to the idea of rule obedience, the concept of being punished for breaking rules. The second kind of morality is known as traditional morality, and it may be identified by the fact that its major emphasis is placed on cultivating connections with other people that are beneficial to both parties

involved. The latter is referred to as post-conventional morality, and it seeks to inform people about global principles as well as their own rights as individuals.

On Literature

If there is any form of misunderstanding, damaging conduct can emerge at any moment along the evolution of these events, which dramatically increases the risk of this happening. While choosing how to proceed with a criminal's case, the legal system considers a variety of different elements; one of these considerations is the manner in which the offender communicates vocally. It was found out by Beitcham et al. (1999), and Snow and Powell also corroborate this notion, that communication issues are frequently misconstrued by the police as evidence of non-compliance (2004).

They noticed that a juvenile criminal's language impairments might affect interviews with the police, interviews with their attorneys, and questions in court since the offender could not understand or appropriately characterize the replies. This was because the offender was a child. This might be because the offender is unable to comprehend the questions being asked or give replies that are truthful to their understanding. As a consequence of this, it is very likely to be misunderstood as disdain for authority, which will therefore make it very probable that the trial will end in a less favorable conclusion, such as harsher fines. It is common for these communication problems to be accompanied by poor body language, which tends to accentuate the sense that the offender does not care about the script. These difficulties with language can be brought on by a variety of factors, including a lack of exposure to language prior to the commencement of puberty (Lenneberg, 1967) and the fact that parents serve as models for language. Bad communication skills can be passed on to their children, which can lead to learning issues (Skinner, 1957). Some of these reasons include a lack of exposure to language prior to the onset of puberty (Lenneberg, 1967); the fact that parents serve as models for their children and that children tend to model their behavior after that of their parents; and the fact that children tend to imitate the behaviors of their parents. Young people who have a history of delinquency are more likely to have a history of low social achievement and learning challenges, as shown by the findings of Bryan et al. (2007). In addition, there are many accounts of people being unable to control their urges. This article covers a variety of issues, including attachment theory, the

development of prosocial behavior, and the influence of language on the judicial system, amongst others.

By examining the ways in which language may have an effect on the system, it demonstrates how developmental sociology can be used to explain criminal conduct. It is demonstrated by this study. In addition to that, the writer of this post draws attention to a number of possible issues that may occur in the future. According to Murray et al. (2007), children whose parents are jailed have a risk of engaging in antisocial conduct that is more than twice as high. The findings of this research give proof that the legal system disrupts the bonding relationships that exist between family members. Yet, developmental psychology can only explain criminal conduct when it is considered in the context of society. None of his hypotheses considers the possibility that criminal conduct may have a biological foundation. None of his theories Because comprehending and defining crime is a challenging endeavor, academics from a diverse array of academic disciplines, such as sociology, psychology, medicine, philosophy, anthropology, economics, and law, work together on crime research. mainly due to the fact that comprehending and defining crime is a challenging endeavor. The academic fields of sociology, psychology, economics, and law are all considered to fall under this umbrella.

According to McGuire, "any action that is openly forbidden by a society's stated rules might simply be declared a crime." "A person is automatically guilty of committing a crime if they engage in any behavior that is specifically forbidden by the written rules of their society." It is possible to envision the conduct of a crime as being anything and everything (2004, p. 3). When someone engages in behavior that violates the law, such as committing theft, fraud, or criminal damage, that kind of action is referred to as a "crime" and is a "criminal act." Despite this, there is a network of relationships between the people who commit crimes, the people who are victimized by those crimes, the police, the courts, and the system of criminal justice. It is possible that the definition of what a society considers to be criminal behavior has evolved from one civilisation to the next throughout human history. Not only does the passage of time and the current condition affect the definition of a criminal act, but so does the fact that crime is a social product and a phenomenon that is socially fashioned. This has an impact on the definition in a way that is distinct from the other two factors. In addition, there is no single type of activity that is universally regarded as being illegal in every circumstance. This is because the interpretation and application of laws can

vary greatly based on the circumstances surrounding the situation. As a result, the kinds of actions that are seen as breaking the law are determined by factors such as society, culture, and the prevailing mentality of the period. It is required to consider a variety of points of view to establish an all-encompassing definition of "crime" based on its inherent characteristics. Within the field of criminal behavior research, the three viewpoints that are utilized most frequently are interactionist, conflict, and consensus interpretations of criminal conduct (Siegel, 2006). (Siegel, 2006). (Siegel, 2006). According to Kenny (1936, page 16), "criminal processes can be followed by a form of outcome (penalty, etc.) that is known to follow these trials" (Kenny, 1936, p. 16). It is necessary that the motivation be illegal. The definition of criminal behavior that emerged from the research that was conducted by a variety of academics is that it entails engaging in activities that are frowned upon by various sectors of society. The rules and penalties that are now in place in a society reflect not only the viewpoints, norms, attitudes, and values that are shared by most of the people of that society but also the laws themselves. The concept of criminal behavior, the structure of the legal system, and the norms and standards of society are inextricably intertwined and interwoven. The term "consensus," which refers to the agreement that a large part of society has reached, is an essential feature of this worldview since it communicates this agreement. Because of this, the word "consensus" is one of the most important aspects of this worldview. This consensus is held by a sizeable portion of individuals who represent all of society.

In addition, Siegel (2006) contends that to have a legal system that is fair, there needs to be a perspective that is supported by most of the people. This is since all eligible people from all eligible classes adequately engage in the process of drafting rules or laws, and laws accurately reflect all eligible classes. In addition to this, this is the case since the laws appropriately depict each kind of organization. Another aspect of crime that can be clearly defined is the conflict viewpoint, which is diametrically opposed to the consensus viewpoint. According to this point of view, strife is an inevitable consequence of human life. According to this point of view, the desire to have power and control over other people is the primary motivation for engaging in illegal action. According to this point of view, society is not a consistent framework; rather, it is made up of several classes and affluent or underprivileged groups of people. In a more general sense, we might speak about a socioeconomic hierarchy existing inside society. To put it another way, privilege and misfortune both contribute to the formation of a hierarchical structure within society. This perspective contends, and this attitude lends credence to its argument, that wealth and power do not circulate

in a community's population in a manner that is equitable to all of its members. The preceding assertion receives additional support from this viewpoint. This makes the inequities that already exist between groups much worse, which in turn leads to conduct that is both aggressive and illegal.

Even though these ideas have a substantial influence, not all sociological research on crime and punishment comes from European sources employing a "top-down" approach. This is true even if the evidence supports the theories. In American sociology, there is also a lengthy history of work that is "bottom-up" in orientation. A thorough empirical investigation of the workings of the criminal justice system is the first step in this area of research. When this foundation has been laid, conceptual frameworks are constructed on top of it. The study of crime and punishment was tackled by the early members of sociology's "Chicago School" with the reform-oriented ideals of the Progressive Period and the philosophical foundations of American pragmatism. This particular school of thought was referred to as the "Chicago School," thus the name. The Chicago method was differentiated by the city's emphasis on doing substantial qualitative research within its huge immigrant groups. This was one of the primary ways in which the city of Chicago approached the problem. This study investigates both the concept of "social disorder" and the concept of "bad social outcomes." Examples of social disorder include dysfunctional families and institutions in society (delinquency, chronic unemployment, and homelessness). These commitments, in turn, helped to stimulate the development of major field-based research on crime and delinquency during the 1920s, 1930s, and early 1940s. This study was conducted in the United States. This research was conducted in a variety of locations around the United States. These studies were conducted in a number of different locations around the United States. Edwin Sutherland's groundbreaking book, *Principles of Criminology*, which developed the "differential relationship," the first general sociological theory of the causation of crime, and the writings of Clifford Shaw and Henry McKay on the social sciences are among the most influential studies that were based on these studies. Other important studies include those that were based on these studies. These two writers were crucial in the development of the study of criminal behavior as a separate academic area. In addition, the research that is being talked about here is some of the most influential that has been spoken about.

The two students who had the biggest effect in Chicago were Howard Becker and Erving Goffman. They continued the Chicago School's concentration on fieldwork while moving away from the

school's reformist and community-based preoccupations. Instead, they investigated the intricate and contradictory nature of the connection that exists between, on the one hand, the manner in which corporate officials classify and commit crime and deviance and, on the other hand, the manner in which individuals begin and pursue careers that are regarded as deviant. As a consequence of this, it was essential for sociologists to have a grasp of both the general public as well as the decision-making processes that take place behind the scenes inside organizations and authorities (such as courts, prisons, asylums, police departments, and probation agencies), charged with the duty of preventing criminal activity and maintaining social order in their respective areas. For the purpose of this interview, which took place against the background of these numerous traditions, four academics got together in order to examine and critique contemporary sociological conceptions regarding criminal conduct and the criminal justice system. They conducted research not only on the institutions responsible for dealing with crime and punishment, but also on the social basis of criminal behavior and deviance. Sociologists and legal experts are both present in this group; sociologists John Hagan and Calvin Morrill and attorneys Bernard Harcourt and Tracey Meares are representatives of their respective professions, respectively. During the University of Chicago Law School's Law Forum's ninth annual symposium, themed "Penalty and Crime," these scholars got together to discuss three significant concerns about the sociology of crime and punishment. They inquired using the following phrases:

- *"What uniquely does sociology contribute to the current study of crime and punishment?"*
And
- *"What does sociology uniquely bring to the modern study of crime and punishment?"*
- *What can we expect from sociological studies on criminal behavior and judicial procedures in the coming years?*
- *How does the research method used by sociologists differ from other intellectual traditions that also deal with the study of criminal behavior and its consequences?*
- *Panelists also examined a fourth issue that focuses on sociologists' normative agendas and value commitments.*

As the panel eventually proceeded to examine this issue, it seemed as though the talk had completed a full circuit by bringing everything back around to where it had started. After a paper

written by criminologist Denis Szabo, political scientist Peter Solomon (1981) pushed academics to investigate how the policy process itself contributed to the creation of criminal justice laws. During the last ten years, Szabo has directed research that has resulted in a publication. Solomon is of the opinion that the interaction of the public, politicians, and specialists at distinct phases of the policy cycle should receive more attention than it now does. These stages involve, among other things, the formulation of an agenda, the making of decisions, the execution of the plan, and its assessment. Sadly, most political scientists choose to disregard the request made of them to pay attention to the issue. ³ The opinions of most sociologists, criminologists, and legal specialists did not concur with this evaluation (though see Rock 1986; Hal, Caputo, and Perry 1992; Petrunik 2003; Campbell 2000; Stenning 1999; Webster and Doob 2007).

Institutions are sets of regulations (electoral rules, constitutional norms, and so on) that can influence strategy and provide certain actors with a preferential position over others. Institutions may be broken down into two categories: governmental and non-governmental. At the very end of the process, institutions have the power to mold preferences as well as the discourse. To begin, actors representing states may have their own distinct goals and sources of power (Peters 2005). The new institutionalism emphasizes politics because it recognizes that policy outcomes are dependent on actors (such as politicians, bureaucrats, judges, and interest groups) operating within and within the constraints and opportunities imposed by institutions. New institutionalism recognizes that the outcomes of policy making depend on the actors (such as politicians, bureaucrats, and interest groups). With this recognition, it is easier to understand why the new institutionalism places such a strong emphasis on politics. This new perspective sheds light on the critical importance of political literacy. This contrasts with the explanations offered by theories such as neo-Marxism, political culture, or rational choice, all of which are either extremely generic, unduly deterministic, or unable to forecast the effects of events that occur. Neo-Marxism is an example of one of these ideas. Neo-Marxism is a school of thought that asserts there is a dialectic of Marxism, and that political culture and rational choice are ways of understanding politics. Neo-Marxism is also an approach to analyzing politics.

Conclusion

Some recent contributions by political scientists to criminal justice issues that use medium-scale approaches that focus on the role of politics and institutional dynamics show that the field has the

potential to shed light on how criminal justice policy is made. These contributions highlight the importance of putting politics and institutional dynamics at the center of one's analysis. These contributions show that the field has a lot to offer when it comes to helping make decisions about criminal justice policies. These contributions show that the field has the potential to produce ideas that can be used to make criminal justice policies. For instance, Leslie Pal (2000) argues that the institutional differences between the parliamentary form of government and the presidential system that is used are important for understanding why the two countries take such different approaches to the regulation of firearms. Friend argues that these institutional differences are important for understanding why the two countries take such different approaches to the regulation of firearms. Pal's argument is that these institutional differences are the key to understanding why the United States and the United Kingdom regulate weapons in such diverse ways. Friend (2000) says that changes in public opinion can't explain why the laws in the two countries are different, since people's views on gun control are more alike than you might think. On top of that, it shows that both of its rather large, organized interests are against putting limits on how many guns people can have. In particular, he is referring to the pro-gun lobby that exists in both nations. By exerting pressure on specific politicians, these organized interests have the potential to stymie or water down any restrictions on the availability of firearms. In a presidential democracy, each of these members of parliament wields a larger sway over the legislative process than their counterparts in parliamentary democracies. This was the case despite strenuous opposition from organized interests and significant concerns voiced by individuals affiliated with the Liberal group. An additional example of an institution-based explanation for policy outcomes that is applicable over the medium term is Janet Hiebert's research (2002). In this body of work, Janet Hiebert investigated the ways in which the Bill of Rights and judicial review influence a variety of policy domains. The findings of this research offer a further illustration of the ramifications for public policy. These changes include making it unlawful to advertise tobacco products, establishing a DNA database, barring law enforcement from conducting unauthorized arrests, and setting procedures for the presenting of evidence and defenses in instances involving sexual assaults. In addition, because of these regulations, making sexually explicit comments on television is now a criminal offense.

Also, laws tend to protect economic, gender, ethnic, and political advantages and positions of power that already exist. This is since laws have a long tradition of favoring particular demographics. The contention that the conflict viewpoint is the more truthful one is bolstered

further by Marxism as a theoretical framework. Being the preeminent mode of economic organization in the world today, capitalism is to blame for the spread of many social subcultures that have arisen as a direct result of its existence. These categories include people who are rich, those who are middle class, and those who have little to no money at all. The prominent group's objective is to preserve or further develop the advantages it currently possesses (Ozdemir, F., and Oner-Ozkan, B., 2017). There are a wide variety of ideas and explanations that have been proposed to unravel the mysteries that surround the nature of illegal activity.

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